

FREQUENCY OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN CASES OF POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME ASSOCIATED WITH INFERTILITY

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Abstract

Objectives: To compare the frequency of metabolic syndrome in patients of polycystic ovary syndrome.**Study Design:** Descriptive cross-sectional study.**Place & Duration of Study:** Department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics, Combined Military Hospital, Sialkot, over a period of 6 months after approval of the synopsis 25-06-2024 to 24-12-2024**Methodology:** A total of 122 women attending the outpatient department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics at Combined Military Hospital, Sialkot, were enrolled after informed written consent. Demographic data were recorded. Blood samples were collected and analyzed in the laboratory. Blood pressure and waist circumference were measured. Metabolic syndrome was labeled as per operational definition. No intervention was performed. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0, and confounding factors were controlled through exclusion criteria.**Results:** A total of 122 women with PCOS were included, with a mean age of 28.88 ± 4.20 years. Most participants were overweight or obese (64.8%). Metabolic syndrome was present in 32.8% of cases. No significant association was observed with age, duration of PCOS, or BMI ($p > 0.05$), although slightly higher frequencies were noted in older, longer-duration, and overweight groups.**Conclusion:** Metabolic syndrome was observed in 33% of women with PCOS, reflecting a considerable burden and emphasizing the importance of early screening and preventive strategies to reduce long-term cardiometabolic risk.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common heterogeneous endocrine disorder affecting women of reproductive age and is frequently associated with hyperandrogenism, anovulation, insulin resistance, and ovarian dysfunction.¹ Its pathogenesis is multifactorial, involving genetic, environmental, and hormonal influences, particularly dysregulation of estrogen, androgens, and anti-Müllerian hormone.² Due to its variable clinical presentation, diagnosis and management

remain challenging, as symptoms differ across age groups and phenotypes.³

Globally, PCOS affects a substantial proportion of women, with NIH-based estimates suggesting a prevalence of 4–10% among reproductive-age women, while WHO reported approximately 116 million affected women worldwide (3.4%).⁴ The burden is further amplified by associated reproductive and metabolic complications, including infertility, menstrual irregularities, and increased cardiometabolic risk, contributing

significantly to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).^{3,4}

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a cluster of conditions including central obesity, hypertension, elevated fasting glucose, raised triglycerides, and reduced high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and is strongly linked with insulin resistance.⁵ Evidence suggests that MetS prevalence has been increasing over time and may manifest early in life. Importantly, PCOS and MetS share overlapping pathophysiological mechanisms, particularly insulin resistance, which links both conditions.⁶

Many studies have reported varying prevalence of MetS in PCOS patients. Giri et al. reported a frequency of 47.1% in Nepal, while Ishak et al. and Tavares et al. reported 43.7% and 33.6%, respectively.^{7,8,9} In contrast, lower prevalence rates were reported in Pakistan by Imtiaz et al. as 27.7% and in China by Li et al. as 19.1%, highlighting significant geographic and population-based variation.^{10,11}

Given this inconsistency in literature, it is important to evaluate the burden of MetS in PCOS patients, particularly in resource-limited settings like Pakistan, where routine screening of all patients may not be feasible. While early detection is desirable to reduce long-term cardiometabolic complications, healthcare resource allocation must be evidence-based. Therefore, this study was designed to determine the frequency of metabolic syndrome in women with PCOS to clarify local burden and contribute to existing evidence.

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted as a descriptive cross-sectional study. The study was carried out in the Department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics, Combined Military Hospital, Sialkot, over a period of 6 months after approval of the synopsis. The sample size consisted of 122 cases, calculated at a 95% confidence level with a 7% margin of error, taking the expected frequency of metabolic syndrome in polycystic ovary syndrome patients as 19.1%.¹¹ Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used. Females aged 20-40 years with polycystic ovary syndrome (as per operational definition) were included. Patients with non-

classical congenital adrenal hyperplasia, Cushing syndrome, thyroid dysfunction, hyperprolactinemia (Prolactin >25 ng/ml), and androgen-producing tumors were excluded.

Polycystic ovarian syndrome was defined as the presence of ovarian cysts on transvaginal ultrasound along with LH/FSH ratio >1, hirsutism, and acne for more than 6 months in cases of primary infertility (inability to conceive after 1 year of unprotected intercourse). Metabolic syndrome was defined according to the IDF criteria as central obesity (waist circumference above ethnicity-specific cut-off) plus any two of the following: triglycerides ≥ 1.7 mmol/L, HDL ≤ 1.3 mmol/L, blood pressure $\geq 135/85$ mmHg, or fasting plasma glucose ≥ 5.6 mmol/L.

A total of 122 women attending the outpatient department and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled after informed written consent. Demographic details were recorded on a structured proforma. Blood samples were collected under aseptic conditions and sent to the laboratory for biochemical analysis. Blood pressure was measured by the researcher, and waist circumference was recorded using a standard measuring tape. Metabolic syndrome was assessed according to the operational definition. No intervention was performed, and patients were managed as per standard departmental protocols. To minimize bias, findings were verified by a senior consultant and recorded by the researcher. Confounding factors were controlled through exclusion criteria.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Numerical variables including age, duration of PCOS, BMI, waist circumference, blood pressure, HDL, fasting plasma glucose, and triglycerides were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables such as metabolic syndrome were expressed as frequency and percentage. Stratification was performed for age and duration of PCOS to assess effect modifiers, and the chi-square test was applied, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 122 women diagnosed with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 28.88

± 4.20 years, with the majority of patients (72, 59.0%) falling in the 18–30 years age group, while 50 (41.0%) were between 31-40 years of age. The mean duration of PCOS was 3.33 ± 1.60 years; 68 (55.7%) patients had a disease duration of ≤3 years, whereas 54 (44.3%) had a duration of more than 3 years. The mean BMI of the study population was 26.56 ± 3.35 kg/m², with 43 (35.2%) women categorized as having normal weight and 79 (64.8%) as overweight or obese. The mean waist circumference was 86.27 ± 14.02 cm. Regarding blood pressure, the mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was 80.51 ± 11.67 mmHg, and the mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) was 129.50 ± 18.35 mmHg. In terms of biochemical

parameters, the mean fasting plasma glucose level was 5.59 ± 1.12 mmol/L, triglycerides were 1.60 ± 0.66 mmol/L, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) level was 1.46 ± 0.38 mmol/L. Data is given in Table I. It was observed that 40 (32.8%) patients had metabolic syndrome as shown in Table II.

No statistically significant association was found between metabolic syndrome and age (p = 0.529), duration of PCOS (p = 0.373), or BMI (p = 0.397). However, a slightly higher frequency was observed in women aged 31-40 years, those with PCOS duration >3 years, and overweight/obese patients compared to their counterparts. Data is given in table III.

Table I: Demographic Characteristics of Women with PCOS

Characteristics	Total (n=122)
Age (years)	28.88±4.20
• 18-30 years	72 (59.0%)
• 31-40 years	50 (41.0%)
Duration of PCOS	3.33±1.60
• ≤3 years	68 (55.7%)
• >3 years	54 (44.3%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.56±3.35
• Normal Weight	43 (35.2%)
• Overweight/Obese	79 (64.8%)
Waist Circumference (cm)	86.27±14.02
DBP (mmHg)	80.51±11.67
SBP (mmHg)	129.50±18.35
Fasting Plasma Glucose	5.59±1.12
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.60±0.66
HDL (mmol/L)	1.46±0.38

Table II: Frequency of MetS in Women with PCOS

Characteristics	n, %age
Metabolic Syndrome	
• Yes	40 (32.8%)
• No	82 (67.2%)

Table III: Frequency of MetS Stratified for Various Sub Groups

Characteristics	Yes	No	p-value
Age (years)			
• 18-30 years	22 (30.6%)	50 (69.4%)	0.529
• 31-40 years	18 (36.0%)	32 (64.0%)	
Duration of PCOS			

• ≤3 years	20 (29.4%)	48 (70.6%)	0.373
• >3 years	20 (37.0%)	34 (63.0%)	
BMI (kg/m²)			
• Normal Weight	12 (27.9%)	31 (72.1%)	0.397
• Overweight/Obese	28 (35.4%)	51 (64.6%)	

Chi Square test, taking p-value ≤0.05 as significant.

DISCUSSION

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder associated with infertility and multiple metabolic disturbances, including metabolic syndrome, which increases long-term cardiovascular and diabetic risk.^{12,13,14} Despite its clinical importance, the reported frequency of metabolic syndrome in PCOS varies widely across different populations due to differences in diagnostic criteria, ethnicity, and lifestyle factors.⁷

¹¹ This inconsistency in the literature has created uncertainty regarding its true burden, particularly in resource-limited settings like Pakistan where local data remain scarce. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the frequency of metabolic syndrome in women with PCOS and to address this gap in existing evidence.

In the present study, the mean age of women with PCOS was 28.88 ± 4.20 years, with most patients belonging to the younger reproductive age group (18–30 years). Similar findings were reported by Anjum et al., who observed a mean age of 27.2 ± 8.13 years in PCOS patients.¹⁵ Li et al. also reported that metabolic and endocrine abnormalities in PCOS predominantly affect younger women of reproductive age.¹¹ However, slightly higher mean ages were reported by Mumtaz et al. (34.58 ± 6.54 years) and Ishak et al., indicating variation across populations.¹⁶

Regarding BMI, 64.8% of patients in the present study were overweight or obese. This is in agreement with Imtiaz et al., who also reported a high proportion of obesity among PCOS patients (29%) and demonstrated a significant association between obesity and metabolic syndrome (p = 0.001).¹⁰ Similarly, Shruthi et al. reported that obese women (BMI ≥27.5 kg/m²) had a markedly higher prevalence of MetS (81.3%).¹⁷ Benharrat et al. further supported this finding by showing that abdominal obesity was present in 94.1% of PCOS women with MetS.¹⁸ These studies collectively

highlight obesity as a key metabolic driver in PCOS, although in our study the association between BMI and MetS was not statistically significant, possibly due to sample size or population differences.

In terms of waist circumference, our study showed a mean value of 86.27 ± 14.02 cm, indicating a tendency toward central obesity in PCOS patients. This is consistent with Giri et al.,⁷ who reported central obesity in 56.6% of cases, and Benharrat et al.,¹⁸ who found abdominal obesity to be one of the most frequent components of metabolic syndrome (94.1%). Similarly, Tavares et al. demonstrated that women with higher abdominal circumference had a significantly increased risk of metabolic syndrome.⁹ These findings reinforce the central role of visceral adiposity in the pathogenesis of metabolic disturbances in PCOS.

Regarding glycemic status, the mean fasting plasma glucose in our study was 5.59 ± 1.12 mmol/L. Giri et al.⁷ reported elevated fasting glucose in 32.07% of PCOS patients with metabolic syndrome, while Shruthi et al.¹⁷ also observed impaired fasting glucose in 37.1% of cases. Li et al.¹¹ further demonstrated significantly higher fasting insulin and metabolic dysregulation in PCOS compared to non-PCOS women, highlighting underlying insulin resistance as a key mechanism.

For lipid profile parameters, the mean triglyceride level in our study was 1.60 ± 0.66 mmol/L, while HDL was 1.46 ± 0.38 mmol/L. These findings are consistent with Giri et al., who reported hypertriglyceridemia in 44.3% and low HDL in 84.9% of PCOS patients.⁷ Similarly, Shruthi et al. observed raised triglycerides in 54.3% and low HDL in 65.7% of cases. Benharrat et al. also reported dyslipidemia, particularly low HDL cholesterol (34.3%), as a common metabolic abnormality.¹⁸ Li et al. further confirmed that dyslipidemia and abnormal lipid parameters are

significantly higher in PCOS compared to controls.¹¹

In relation to blood pressure, the present study demonstrated mean systolic and diastolic blood pressures of 129.50 ± 18.35 mmHg and 80.51 ± 11.67 mmHg, respectively. Similar trends were observed in Mumtaz et al., who reported mean SBP and DBP of 130.05 ± 12.15 mmHg and 85.59 ± 9.40 mmHg.¹⁶ Shruthi et al. also identified elevated blood pressure in 40% of PCOS patients with metabolic syndrome, while Benharrat et al. reported hypertension in 56.9% of affected individuals.¹⁸ These findings indicate that blood pressure abnormalities are an important component of metabolic risk in PCOS. In the present study, the frequency of metabolic syndrome (MetS) among women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) was 32.8%, indicating a considerable cardiometabolic burden in this population. This finding is comparable with studies by Mumtaz et al.,¹⁶ who reported a prevalence of 31.6%, and Tavares et al.,⁹ who observed a frequency of 33.6% among PCOS women. Similarly, Shruthi et al.¹⁷ reported a prevalence of 45.7%, while Anjum et al.¹⁵ documented a higher frequency of 46.4%, suggesting variability across populations. In contrast, a lower prevalence was reported by Imtiaz et al.¹⁰ in Pakistan (27.7%), and Ishak et al.⁸ in Malaysia (43.4%), reflecting regional differences, diagnostic criteria, and population characteristics. Overall, our findings align with most regional studies, confirming that approximately one-third of PCOS patients are affected by MetS.

This study highlights the frequency of metabolic syndrome in PCOS using standardized IDF criteria in a well-defined sample. Limitations include single-center design and limited sample size, reducing generalizability. Future research should involve multicenter studies with larger populations to explore causative factors and long-term cardiometabolic outcomes in PCOS patients.

CONCLUSION

Metabolic syndrome was observed in 33% of women with PCOS, reflecting a considerable burden and emphasizing the importance of early

screening and preventive strategies to reduce long-term cardiometabolic risk.

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2,3

Substantial contributions to concept, study design
Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

REFERENCES

- Sadeghi HM, Adeli I, Calina D, Docea AO, Mousavi T, Daniali M, et al. Polycystic ovary syndrome: a comprehensive review of pathogenesis, management, and drug repurposing. *Int J Mol Sci* 2022;23(2):583-9.
- Witchel SF, Oberfield SE, Peña AS. Polycystic ovary syndrome: pathophysiology, presentation, and treatment with emphasis on adolescent girls. *J Endocr Soc* 2019;3(8):1545-73.
- Fahs D, Salloum D, Nasrallah M, Ghazeeri G. Polycystic ovary syndrome: pathophysiology and controversies in diagnosis. *Diagnostics (Basel)* 2023;13(9):1559-65.
- Singh S, Pal N, Shubham S, Sarma DK, Verma V, Marotta F, et al. Polycystic ovary syndrome: etiology, current management, and future therapeutics. *J Clin Med* 2023;12(4):1454-9.

- Fu L, Xie N, Qu F, Zhou J, Wang F. The association between polycystic ovary syndrome and metabolic syndrome in adolescents: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Reprod Sci* 2023;30(1): 28-40.
- Zaemzadeh N, Sadatmahalleh SJ, Ziaei S, Kazemnejad A, Mottaghi A, Mohamadzadeh N, et al. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in four phenotypes of PCOS and its relationship with androgenic components among Iranian women: A cross-sectional study. *Int J Repord BioMed* 2020;18(4):253-64.
- Giri A, Joshi A, Shrestha S, Chaudhary A. Metabolic syndrome among patients with polycystic ovarian syndrome presenting to a tertiary care hospital: a descriptive cross-sectional study. *JNMA: J Nepal Med Assoc* 2022;60(246):137-41.
- Ishak A, Kadir AA, Hussain NH, Ismail SB. Prevalence and characteristics of metabolic syndrome among polycystic ovarian syndrome patients in Malaysia. *Int J Collab Res Intern Med Public Health* 2012;4(8):1577-88.
- Tavares A, Barros RC. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome in the different phenotypes of polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Rev Bras Ginecol Obstet* 2019;41:37-43.
- Imtiaz S, Gul P, Shahnawaz S, Zarrar T, Kubra K, Akram S. Frequency of metabolic syndrome in patients with polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Life Sci* 2023;4(3):290-6.
- Li R, Yu G, Yang D, Li S, Lu S, Wu X, et al. Prevalence and predictors of metabolic abnormalities in Chinese women with PCOS: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Endocr Disord* 2014;14(1):1-8.
- Lentscher JA, Decherney AH. Clinical presentation and diagnosis of polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Clin Obstet Gynecol* 2021;64(1):3-11.
- Siddiqui S, Mateen S, Ahmad R, Moin S. A brief insight into the etiology, genetics, and immunology of polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS). *J Aassis Reprod Genet* 2022;39(11):2439-73.
- Hallajzadeh J, Khoramdad M, Karamzad N, Almasi-Hashiani A, Janati A, Ayubi E, et al. Metabolic syndrome and its components among women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Cardiovasc Thorac Res* 2018;10(2):25-69.
- Anjum S, Askari S, Riaz M, Basit A. Clinical presentation and frequency of metabolic syndrome in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: an experience from a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. *Cureus* 2020;12(12):e11860.
- Mumtaz NM, Ashraf AA, Abid SA, Niaz SN, Ahmed SA, Jabbar S. Metabolic syndromes in females with polycystic ovary syndrome. *J Akhtar Saeed Med Dent Coll* 2021;3(04):169-74.
- Shruthi S, Lakshmi G, Washington JK, TS M, Washington K. Prevalence and predictors of metabolic syndrome in women with polycystic ovarian syndrome: a cross-sectional study. *Cureus* 2025;17(12):e98869.
- Benharrat LI, Senouci A, Benhabib W, Mekki K. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: Relationship with lifestyle and cardiometabolic biomarkers. *Rom J Diabetes Nutr Metab Dis* 2021;28(4):383-90.